

RE-DWELL Workshop 3 (Zagreb)

Deliverable 3.3

Lead Beneficiary: UNIZG – University of Zagreb, Faculty of Law

Date: May 30, 2023 (m32)

Submission date: October 5, 2023 (m37)

Version: 1

Dissemination level: Public

www.re-dwell.eu

RE-DWELL “Delivering affordable and sustainable housing in Europe” has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956082

The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

RE-DWELL

Deliverable 3.3 RE-DWELL Workshop 3 (Zagreb)

Version 1

Authors:

Gojko Bežovan (UNIZG)

Marko Horvat (UNIZG)

Version	Date	Authors
0.1	12.7. 2023	Marko Horvat (UNIZG)
0.2	29.8.2023	Gojko Bezovan (UNIZG)
0.3	2.10.23	Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL)
1	5.10.2023	Lisa Kinnear (proof-reading) (La Salle-URL)

Table of contents

Executive summary.....	1
1. Introduction.....	2
1.1. Contribution of local partners.....	2
1.2. Participants	3
1.3. RTM and TS training activities	3
1.4. Dissemination	7
2. Programme.....	9
2.1. Activities.....	11
2.2. Evaluation	26
3. Conclusion.....	33
Annex 1 –WP4 presentations.....	34

Executive summary

Three international workshops have been planned to take place in Lisbon (2021), Budapest (2022), and Zagreb (2023) as part of the RE-DWELL project. The third and final workshop, organised by the University of Zagreb, Faculty of Law, Institute for Social Policy (UNIZG) was carried out during the third year of the project activities in Zagreb, from March 29 to 31, 2023.

The theme of the Zagreb workshop, “Policy and financing for affordable and sustainable housing”, was approached from a transdisciplinary perspective, focusing on urban renewal, social and rental housing, and social mix. The workshop programme fulfilled various objectives: to follow up on the development of the ESRs’ research by fostering networking between the individual research projects, to conduct training activities related to two structured courses (RMT3 and TS3), to continue with the collaborative research work (vocabulary and case studies library) and to engage local stakeholders in the networking actions (non-academic sectors, local administrations and civic organizations concerned with sustainable and affordable housing). Furthermore, activities focusing on production of transdisciplinary affordable and sustainable housing research framework took place, as laid down in WP4.

Day 1 of the workshop started with the introductory rounds from Gojko Bežovan (UNIZG) and Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL) which were followed by lectures given by Tihomir Jukić, professor from the Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb, on “Urban renewal of the historical part of the City of Zagreb after the last earthquake”, and by Leandro Madrazo on transdisciplinarity in housing research. These sessions were followed by the ESRs’ presentations on WP4 tasks prepared in advance. In the afternoon, Gojko Bežovan gave an overview lecture of “Housing challenges in the city of Zagreb” that also served as an introduction to the site visits to three housing developments in the city of Zagreb.

The second day commenced with guest lecturer Montserrat Pareja-Eastaway from the University of Barcelona who gave a talk on the topic “Beyond the market: transforming the housing agenda in Europe”. In addition, there was a joint session of the courses “RMT3: Transferring Research Findings to Community Stakeholders” and “TS3: Communication and Dissemination; Engagement and Impact,” focusing on the topic of “Methods and Communications with Non-Academic Stakeholders.”

The third day commenced with a lecture from Ana Vaz Milheiro (ISCTE-University Institute of Lisbon) on “Portuguese residential strategies before the Carnation Revolution: designing affordable neighbourhoods”. Following the lecture, ESRs engaged in the reflective writing on relevant WP4 tasks followed by the lively discussion. A management board meeting took place during the workshop, with the participation of beneficiaries and the ESR representatives.

1. Introduction

The third workshop was held between 29 and 31 March 2023 at the premises of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing of University of Zagreb. This workshop is part of the RE-DWELL network-wide activities, following the conference in Grenoble, France, which took place on 8-9 December 2022, and before the summer school at the University of Reading, United Kingdom. It was the last out of the three workshops planned in the RE-DWELL project. The aim of the workshop was to foster the knowledge exchange between ESRs, supervisors and non-academic organisations on the challenges and opportunities on “Policy and financing in affordable and sustainable housing”. “The [programme](#) included sessions dedicated to addressing the workshop's topic from multiple perspectives and featured guest speakers from other universities. Lessons learned from the evaluation of previous network activities, namely the Budapest Workshop in March 2022, and the Valencia Summer School in July 2022, were considered in the design of the programme. Specifically, we strengthened the preparatory activities conducted before the workshop, reduced the time allocated to presentations in favour of group discussions, and engaged the External Advisory Board members in the network.

Throughout the different activities of the programme, ESRs had the opportunity to demonstrate their ability to present and communicate research ideas and outputs to expert and non-expert audiences, improve their understanding of transdisciplinary research methodologies and their application to their own projects, develop personal skills and self-management competences, and learn on the local urban and housing developments engaging with local stakeholders during the visits to three sites.

This report summarizes the work done during the workshop. It encompasses the programme of activities, the work done by ESRs before the workshop, the RTM3 and TS3 courses in-person activities, and the workshop evaluation by ESRs, supervisors and co-supervisors.

The report is also useful for faculty members from other institutions seeking to learn more about the work done in RE-DWELL, whose fundamental aim is to increase the knowledge and understanding on the compatibility between affordable and sustainable housing across Europe through a holistic and transdisciplinary research and training programme.

1.1. Contribution of local partners

The UNIZG was in charge of the organization of the workshop. The cooperation with stakeholders from the planned site visits provided crucial for a meaningful learning experience about the various challenges in terms of affordable and sustainable housing. Participants had a chance to meet residents, managers and developers and directly exchange opinions on the challenges they personally experience and how such processes might be improved. The participating local stakeholders were:

- Two residents in Podbrežje project (site visit 1), Mirko Poljak employed as a professor at University of Zagreb, and Petra Matijaš employed in office of City of Zagreb.
- Three stakeholders in Novi Jelkovec (site visit 2) neighbourhood
Juro Ivelj, working for the city of Zagreb, housing department
Željka Mazzi, resident and active in local civil society organization
Iva Klak Mrsić, manager of the city library/in the neighbourhood of Novi Jelkovec

- Ivan Vučemil, Manager in developer company of a high-end residential project, VMD group (site visit 3)

The consortium is very thankful to professor Tihomir Jukić, an expert in urban and spatial planning and landscape architecture, for providing insights about the building and urban renovation challenges in Zagreb after the latest earthquake.

1.2. Participants

27 participants attended the workshop in Budapest, including 12 ESRs, 9 supervisors/co-supervisors, 1 representative of a local partner organisation and 3 guest speakers:

- B1 FUNITEC (La Salle-URL), Spain. Leandro Madrazo (project coordinator); Nuria Marti (supervisor); Saskia Furman (ESRs)
- B3 University of Sheffield, United Kingdom. Aya Elghandour (ESR)
- B4 University of Zagreb, Croatia. Gojko Bezovan (supervisor); Marko Horvat (ESR)
- B5 CSS Hungarian Academy of Sciences Centre of Excellence, Hungary Adrienne Csizmady (supervisor); Anna Martin (ESR)
- B6 University of Cyprus, Cyprus. Nadia Charalambous (supervisor), Effrosyni Roussou, Andreas Panagidis (ESRs)
- B7 Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain. Carla Sentieri (supervisor); Zoe Tzika (ESR)
- B8 TU Delft, Netherlands. Marja Elsinga (supervisor), Tijn Croon, Alex Fernández (ESRs)
- B9 ISCTE- Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, Portugal. Alexandra Paio (supervisor); Androniki Pappa (ESR)
- B10 University of Reading, United Kingdom. Lorraine Farrelly (supervisor), Leonardo Ricaurte (ESR)
- B11 University of Grenoble, Paulette Duarte (supervisor), Christophe Verrier (ESR)
- P1 CERANEO, Ana Zadelj Kovač (partner organisation)
- Guest speakers: Tihomir Jukić, Montserrat Pareja-Eastaway, Ana Vaz Milheiro

1.3. RTM and TS training activities

The first sessions of the RMT3 and TS3 courses in the workshop took place during the workshop in a shared timeslot.

RMT3 session + TS3 session

As outlined in the programme the "RMT3: Transferring Research Findings to Community Stakeholders" and "TS3: Communication and Dissemination; Engagement and Impact" (see Figures 1 and 2), specific activities were scheduled to be completed before the workshop. Prior to the meeting, ESRs worked in teams of three, conducting preliminary research to gather information about secondments, case studies, and their Ph.D. research. This information was utilized during the hands-on session to explore various methods and communication channels that ESRs could employ to share their research findings. They shared their experiences from

their research and secondments, discussing effective ways to communicate their research results to stakeholders, identify target groups for their research outcomes, and review the methods used for communication.

Rereach Methods and Tools 3 (RMT3)

Figure 1. RMT3 course structure as integrated with the network activities.

Figure 2. TS3 course structure as integrated with the network activities.

1.4. Dissemination

There were dissemination activities before and during the event, on different media (website, social media, emails), and for diverse target groups: researchers, local associations, faculty, PhD students, policymakers and the general public. The event was communicated in the RE-DWELL website and Newsletter #3 on November 2022 (Figure 3), as well as in its social media channels (Figure 4) before and during the activities of the workshop on Twitter. The event was also disseminated locally through the University of Zagreb channels, such as email list and weekly bulleting (Figure 5). A UNIZG video maker recorded the lectures delivered by the two guest speakers. The recordings are available on the RE-DWELL website for public dissemination.

Networking activities

The programme of activities of the [Valencia summer school \(July 2022\)](#) aimed at fostering the exchange of knowledge across early-stage researchers (ESRs), supervisors and non-academic organisations, on the challenges and opportunities in Inclusive co-design and community planning of affordable and sustainable housing.

The first RE-DWELL conference organized by Université Grenoble Alpes will provide a platform for multiple actors involved in housing policy, planning, design and construction to discuss "Housing co-creation for tomorrow's cities". Four keynote speakers and twenty-two abstract presentations are included in the two-day [programme](#).

The third RE-DWELL workshop will take place at the University of Zagreb, from 29 to 31 March 2023, and the third summer school at the University of Reading, from 3 to 7 July 2023.

Figure 3. Communication in RE-DWELL Newsletter # 3

Figure 4. Dissemination during the workshop on RE-DWELL's Twitter page

28-31 March 2023
RE-DWELL
Workshop #3
Zagreb
Policy and financing for affordable and sustainable housing
Faculty of Law, Institute for Social Policy, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Venue: Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing (FER) Building D, Uroška ulica 3, 10 000 Zagreb

European Commission
This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement for 101019150

The workshop will explore the links between different fields and stakeholders from research activities in diverse settings. These include individual research projects, exchanges, and collective research endeavors (using relevant terminology and examples). The External Advisory Board will contribute to discussions on the importance of adopting a transdisciplinary approach for achieving sustainable and cost-effective housing. A collaborative effort between the "Research, Methods, and Tools" and "Transferable Skills" courses will concentrate on techniques and instruments for promoting communication and knowledge exchange among academic and non-academic entities. Site visits and lectures from local academics will offer insights into policy and financing approaches for supplying affordable housing in Zagreb.

PROGRAMME

Figure 5. Communication before the workshop on UNIZG channel

During the workshop, ESRs had an interactive discussion on how they apply a transdisciplinary approach to their research (Figure 6)

Figure 6. Collaborative work session with ESRs

2. Programme

The programme was available on the [project website](#) before the start of the workshop, and local academic community was previously informed of the programme. One PhD student from the Department of Sociology at the University of Zagreb who is working on housing and urban research attended lectures of guest speakers. It was an on-site event, without the possibility of joining online. It started with an informal dinner for participants on 27 March, Tuesday, and ended on 31 March, Friday (Table 1).

Table 1. Programme of the workshop

Day	Timetable	Activities
DAY 0 Tuesday, 28 March, 2023	20:00	Informal gathering and dinner for early arrivals at "Bistro Fotic"
DAY 1 Wednesday, 29 March, 2023	09:00 to 09:15	Welcome- Introduction to day's programme
	09:15 to 10:00	Urban renewal of the historical part of the City of Zagreb after earthquake
	10:00 to 10:15	Coffee break
	10:15 to 11:15	Beyond transdisciplinarity: the "pluri-epistemic" as a basis for understanding housing and urbanism
	11:15 to 13:00	ESRs presentation of WP4 activity
	13:00 to 14:00	Lunch break
	14:00 to 14:45	Challenges of housing in the city of Zagreb
	15:00 to 18:45	Guided tour
	20:00	Dinner at "Didov san"
DAY 2 Thursday, 30 March, 2023	09:00 to 09:15	Introduction to day's programme
	09:15 to 10:15	Beyond the market: transforming the housing agenda in Europe
	10:15 to 10:30	Coffee break
	10:30 to 13:00	Discussions with EAB members about presentations of previous day
	13:00 to 14:00	Lunch break
	14:00 to 17:00	RMT3/TS3 session
	15:30 to 15:45	Coffee break
	15:45 to 17:00	RMT3/TS3 session
		20:00

DAY 3 Friday, 31 March, 2023	09:00 to 09:15	Introduction to day's programme
	09:15 to 10:15	Portuguese residential strategies before the Carnation Revolution: designing affordable Neighbourhoods
	10:15 to 10:30	Coffee break
	10:30 to 12:00	ESRs hands-on exercise – reflective writing on previous WP4 task
	10:30 to 12:00	Management Board meeting
	12:00 to 13:00	Discussion hands-on exercise
	13:00 to 14:00	Lunch break
	14:00 to 17:00	Meetings ESRs and supervisors
	15:30 to 15:45	Coffee break
	15:45 to 17:00	Meetings ESRs and supervisors (continuation)
	20:00	Dinner at “Purger”

2.1. Activities

DAY 0

Tuesday, 28 March

Informal gathering and dinner for early arrivals at "Bistro Fotic"

DAY 1

Wednesday, 29 March

Welcome

The workshop started with a short welcoming from the head of the Institute of Social policy, Gojko Bežovan (Figure 7), professor at the University of Zagreb, Faculty of Law (UNIZG), and the RE-DWELL project coordinator, Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL).

Figure 7. RE-DWELL Zagreb workshop welcome speech by Gojko Bežovan

Guest speech

Tihomir Jukić, from the Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb (Figure 8), delivered a lecture on “Urban renewal of the historical part of the City of Zagreb after the last earthquake”.

Figure 8. Presentation by Tihomir Jukić

Guest speech (cancelled)

The planned lecture “Beyond trans-disciplinarity: the ‘pluri-epistemic’ as a basis for understanding housing and urbanism” could not be given due to a last-minute indisposition of the guest speaker. Instead, the project coordinator delivered a presentation on transdisciplinary research based on a previous publication of the guest lecturer who had been scheduled to give a talk (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Presentation by Leandro Madrazo

ESRs presentation of WP4 activity

This session was moderated by Marja Elsinga from TU Delft (Figure 10) and consisted of group presentations by ESRs on the tasks assigned in WP4 activities. The purpose of this activity was to reflect on the connections between the knowledge chunks collaboratively generated in the RE-DWELL project so far. The objective was to highlight issues related to transdisciplinary research, specifically the integration of knowledge from diverse disciplines and engagement with stakeholders outside academia, to address complex and multifaceted problems. This activity built upon the secondment experiences presented at the Supervisory Board meeting held on November 15, 2022.

Figure 10. Presentation of WP4 session by Marja Elsinga

The project's resources to carry out this activity included case Studies, vocabulary entries, secondment reports and ESRs' research project abstracts. These resources were to interrelate the three RE-DWELL research areas underpinning affordable and sustainable housing (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Structure of the assignment

This activity was meant to be a practical exercise in transdisciplinary research across various fields, involving non-academic stakeholders (partner organisations, and other) in the reflections.

Prior to the meeting in Zagreb, ESRs worked in teams of three and to reflect on selected resources. Each team consisted of researchers working on one of the three main research areas of the project (Table 2).

Table 2. WP4 team composition

	Design, Planning and Building	Community Participation	Policy and Financing
Team 1	Tijn Croon	Carolina Martin	Androniki Pappa
Team 2	Saskia Furman	Phryne Roussou	Christophe Verrier
Team 3	Aya Elghandour	Anna Martin	Zoe Tzika
Team 4	Mahmoud Alsaeed	Marko Horvat	Leonardo Ricaurte
Team 5	Annette Davis	Alex Fernández	Andreas Panagidis

During the presentations, each group presented their reflections on how they combine project resources and their individual understanding of transdisciplinarity in their respective fields of study. This task was of a particular importance for ESRs to learn new skills in comprehending the relevance of transdisciplinarity in their individual research, and how to coherently communicate these relationships to peers and supervisors. The outcomes of the discussion provided valuable inputs for the deliverables of WP4 “Transdisciplinary affordable and sustainable housing research framework”.

Teams presentations are shown in Annex 1.

Lunch

Participants had lunch at the facilities of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, University of Zagreb (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Lunch at the Faculty restaurant

Housing challenges in the city of Zagreb

In the afternoon session, Gojko Bežovan delivered a presentation on "Housing Challenges in the City of Zagreb." The topics discussed included the legacy of communist housing policies and the reforms implemented during the 1990s. Professor Bežovan also touched upon the new beginnings in housing policy at the start of the 2000s, highlighting the social housing pilot projects and their role in fostering housing innovation. He examined the impact of the 2008 financial crisis on the economy and housing sector. Additionally, he discussed the current housing loan subsidy programme and addressed the escalating housing prices in Zagreb, the Adriatic region, and Croatia, emphasizing their influence on affordability.

This lecture served as an insightful introduction to the guided tour that followed.

Guided tour

A pre-booked bus transported the group to three sites in Zagreb, each representing a case of affordable and sustainable housing scheme: Podbrežje, Novi Jelkovec and Kvart Heinzelova-Darwinaova.

PODBREŽJE

The housing estate Podbrežje is situated in the area that is only 6 km to the south from the main City square. The settlement area includes 19.4 hectares. This settlement will greatly contribute to increasing the quality of life in the neighbouring settlements which were built compliant with other standards in the 1970s and 1980s (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Site visit to Podbrežje and meeting with residents

The planned facilities include:

- 11 detached residential buildings, heights up to 9 floors with 1,800 flats
- two kindergartens
- a primary and a secondary school
- a culture and information centre
- a swimming pool complex and a sports centre
- a health centre with general and specialized clinics
- a community centre for the elderly
- advisory centres for social protection of children and adult
- parks, 6 playgrounds for ages 0-6 years and 6 playgrounds for ages 7-18
- entire settlement area is pedestrian and wheelchair friendly

The project implementation commenced in 2016 with the construction of three building blocks comprising 608 flats. This initiative was a pivotal component of the Zagreb model for housing construction, which stood in contrast to the national and highly centralized POS (Publicly Owned Apartments) programme. The concept of social mix, integrating affordable homeownership, social rental, and public rental units, was successfully implemented in this settlement during the development process.

This programme was inspired by the City of Zagreb's initiative to offer affordable homeownership opportunities to young academics, supplemented by extra subsidies from the City's budget. A needs assessment survey was conducted, revealing that 351 young academics had shown interest in the programme. However, the majority of them were not eligible for affordable housing loans, leading to only two contracts being realized under this initiative.

Recently, the City's mayor announced plans to invest in the construction of 300 flats for social and public renting within this settlement. Moreover, a direct public bus line to downtown was established, enhancing the accessibility and convenience of the area.

NOVI JELKOVEC

The construction of the settlement commenced in October 2006, and by April 2009 the first tenants had moved in. The settlement comprises 53 buildings, housing 2,713 flats and providing space for 200 businesses, currently housing approximately 12,000 residents.

Among the total flats available, 1,263 were allocated for controlled market prices, making them affordable for young families seeking their first home. Additionally, there were 800 flats designated for social rental housing and 650 flats for the public rental programme, catering specifically for young families with children. This intentional mix of social rental housing, public rental housing, and privately owned housing promotes a diverse and inclusive community.

The settlement boasts essential amenities, including a primary school and kindergarten, although these facilities are currently over capacitated. There is also a secondary school equipped with a sports hall, swimming pool, and outdoor sports facilities. Furthermore, the settlement features a health care and social care centre unit. The public library (Figures 14, 15) serves as a hub for social interactions, fostering community engagement and connectivity.

Figure 14. Site visit to Novi Jelkovec library and social centre for the community

Figure 15. Presentation and discussion at the library and social centre

Additionally, there are plans in place for the construction of a Cultural Center spanning 1,500 sq. m., designed to host various activities such as theatre performances, music schools, and foreign language classes. Funding for this centre might be obtained from the European Union. The local council, as an integral part of the city's governing structure, is actively involved in the development and enhancement of the settlement.

The concept of self-organized associations plays a crucial role, with dedicated members working to improve the living conditions within the settlement. Despite past challenges, the settlement has made great strides in overcoming a negative image and addressing integration issues, particularly concerning Roma families.

Empirical evidence from two surveys indicates a notable improvement in the overall quality of life within the settlement. To further enhance accessibility, two public bus lines have been created, ensuring convenient transport options for the residents.

KVART HEINZELOVA-DARWINAOVA

The settlement area built by the VMD group spans 8.3 hectares and boasts an excellent location within the city, making it a prime example of top-quality housing. The ground floor spaces are designated to service-oriented businesses catering for the residents' needs, while the eight-storey buildings house a total of 400 flats. These structures adhere to the distinctive VMD "standard" and were constructed following green building principles. Rainwater collected on-site is efficiently utilized for watering the green areas, showcasing an environmentally conscious approach. Once construction is completed, the management of the buildings will be overseen by VMD services.

The flats vary in size, ranging from 50 to 150 square meters, with the majority falling within the 70-80 square meter range. A significant effort has been made to create a vibrant and inclusive community environment by incorporating essential amenities such as a playground, kindergarten, public park, and pedestrian pathways (Figure 16).

Overall, this private housing development exemplifies a meticulous focus on quality, sustainability, and community well-being.

Figure 16. Site visit to *Kvart Heinzelova-Darwinaova*

DAY 2

Thursday, 30 March

The day 2 started with the introduction of the day's activities by host Gojko Bežovan

Guest speech

Invited speaker was Montserrat Pareja-Eastaway (Figure 17), professor at the Universitat de Barcelona, and member of the RE-DWELL External Advisory Board, who delivered an inspiring lecture on the topic “Beyond the market: transforming the housing agenda in Europe”. The recorded speech is available on the RE-DWELL [website](#).

To implement the agenda and find innovative solutions, housing needs to be addressed holistically, all the dimensions together. The solutions do not depend only on money.

[#ZagrebWorkshop](#) [#MSCA](#) [#ResearchImpactEU](#) [#H2020](#)

Figure 17. Presentation by guest speaker Montserrat Pareja-Eastaway

Discussions with EAB members about presentations of previous day

This session was prepared and moderated by Marja Elsinga (Figure 18). Marja selected some of the best examples from the ESRs presentations of the day before to discuss possible progress towards the RE-DWELL assessment framework.

Figure 18. Presentation by Marja Elsinga on the assessment framework

Lunch break

RMT3/TS3 sessions

This session was a collaborative effort between the RMT3 and TS3 courses, co-organized by Adrienne Csizmady (RMT3) (Figure 19) and Lorraine Farrelly (TS3) (Figure 20). The central theme in both courses revolved around enhancing communication strategies with specific target groups. The activity spanned the entirety of the day.

Figure 19. Presentation by Adrienne Csizmady

Figure 20. Presentation by Lorraine Farrelly

The objective of this activity was to assist ESRs in determining the most effective methods for disseminating their findings to non-academic stakeholders. This initiative was built upon the experiences gained during their secondments and the outcomes of the project, including case studies, vocabulary entries, secondment reports, and abstracts of ESRs' research projects. Importantly, this effort served as a complement to the work carried out in WP4, as it facilitated the integration of the three main research areas of RE-DWELL (Design, planning, and building; Community participation; and Policy and financing) by linking them through the project's outcomes.

The activity was structured into two stages:

Stage 1: To be completed before the workshop.

Stage 2: To be initiated during the workshop and finalized by mid-April 2023.

Stage 1

During the first stage, ESRs collaborated in teams to gather essential information, including:

- **Actors:** Non-academic organizations they interacted with during their secondments.
- **Organizations:** Entities potentially interested in the outcomes of the secondment work, identifying specific target groups.
- **Methods:** Strategies employed for disseminating scientific results to non-academic organizations both during and after the secondment.
- **Communication tools:** Tools used to share their findings effectively.

Each team presented the compiled information in a concise format during the session, highlighting their research findings and insights.

Stage 2

In the second stage of this activity, conducted during the workshop, the focus shifted to identifying and mapping the target groups/non-academic actors, methods, and communication tools. The goal was to understand their connections to the three core RE-DWELL research areas: Design, planning, and building; Community participation; and Policy and financing.

Each team's task was to create a visual map and provide a brief explanation, highlighting the interactions between these research areas. To facilitate interactive participation among the ESRs, a Miro board was set up, allowing real-time collaboration and visualization (see Figure 21).

The outcomes of this task served as input for the activities in WP4.

DAY 3

Friday, 31 March

The final day started with the introduction to the day's programme by the host Gojko Bežovan.

Guest speech

The guest speaker was Ana Vaz Milheiro, professor at the University Institute of Lisbon and member of the RE-DWELL External Advisory Board, who gave a lecture on “Portuguese residential strategies before the Carnation Revolution: designing affordable neighbourhoods” (Figure 22). In her lecture, professor Vaz Milheiro addressed the construction of an image of the middle-class through the housing states built in the 1950-60 in Lisbon. The recorded speech can be found on the public RE-DWELL [website](#).

Figure 22. Presentation of the guest speaker Ana Vaz Milheiro

ESRs hands-on exercise – reflective writing on previous WP4 task

A hands-on exercise was conducted in parallel with the Management Board meeting, specifically dedicated to discussing the project development challenges with ESR representatives.

This activity constituted the second stage of the transdisciplinary research in practice task under WP4 and was prepared and facilitated by Marja Elsinga (Figure 23). The focus was on composing a text based on the reflections that had previously been presented and discussed. The outcome of this task will be a document of 5-10 pages per group, to be finalized in April 2023.

Figure 23. Group moderation by Marja Elsinga

2.2. Evaluation

The workshop was evaluated by all the participants through an anonymous online survey. The main goal of the survey was to evaluate their experience and to detect any elements that could be improved in future workshops and summer schools.

The online survey was answered by 12 ESRs and 8 supervisors/co-supervisors.

Participants were asked their opinion on the following aspects of the Zagreb workshop (Table 3). In the first part of the survey questions, participants were asked to rate various aspects of the workshop. In the second part, they had to identify what they had particularly liked and what could have been done better. At the end of the survey, they could add comments and recommendations for future network activities.

Table 3. Zagreb Workshop: online evaluation

Questions	Answers (total)	Supervisors/Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
How would you rate the organization of the workshop? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	20	4,75	4,42	4,55
"Urban renewal of the historical part of the City of Zagreb after earthquake" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	18	4,63	4,00	4,28
Please evaluate "Discussion about transdisciplinarity and affordable housing" (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	18	4,38	2,90	3,56
Please evaluate "RE-DWELL transdisciplinary research and assessment framework" (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	18	4,25	4,00	4,11

Please evaluate "ESRs presentation of WP4 activity" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	18	4,25	3,90	4,06
Please evaluate "Challenges of housing in the city of Zagreb" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	16	4,30	3,89	4,06
Please evaluate "Guided tour" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	17	4,50	3,44	3,94
Please evaluate "Beyond the market: transforming the housing agenda in Europe", session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	20	4,75	4,50	4,60
Please evaluate "Discussions with EAB members about presentations of previous day", session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	20	3,88	3,58	3,70
Please evaluate "RMT3 introduction" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	18	4,29	3,55	3,83
Please evaluate "TS3 hands on session, Lorraine Farrelly" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	19	4,43	3,83	4,05
Please evaluate "Portuguese residential strategies before the Carnation Revolution: designing affordable neighbourhoods", session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	19	4,43	3,83	4,05
Please evaluate "ESRs hands-on exercise – reflective writing on previous WP4 task" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	18	4,00	3,67	3,78
Please evaluate "Meetings ESRs and supervisors" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	17	3,67	3,55	3,59

This section provides qualitative descriptions based on the questions above. The following list of questions is followed by the written answers:

- Urban renewal of the historical part of the City of Zagreb after earthquake

"Very insightful and relevant for the topic."

"It provided a different perspective on the challenges faced by some European countries. The explanations of the real political challenges that the city is facing reminded me of similar challenges in other countries. Additionally, Gojko added a political perspective to enable us to have a comprehensive overview of the various threads in those challenges."

"It was a pertinent and detailed presentation that introduced us to the local context, housing struggles and the historical processes that have led to its current state."

“Very informative session and a nice introduction to the city of Zagreb.”

“Informative on the local context.”

- Discussion about transdisciplinarity and affordable housing

“It was interesting to hear Leandro's reflection and critical review of Salama's work. The part that resonated with me the most was when Leandro explained that transdisciplinarity calls for humility and the ability to listen to others' points of view while also adopting critical thinking.”

“Even though there was an unanticipated change in the programme, the session was a good conversation starter for the other sessions that followed.”

“Very much appreciated the adaptability of the schedule. It would be nice to reschedule this session as it seems a useful contribution for our perception of transdisciplinarity.”

“The initial part, where the paper was summarised was rather unnecessary, as this has been a core article within the collective re-dwell literature, and I am certain there is no ESR that has not read it. I believe we would have benefitted more from an ESR session where we discuss the stage of our individual projects, and provide each other with feedback.”

- RE-DWELL transdisciplinary research and assessment framework

“It was good to get some clarity on the topic.”

“This is the first time I have seen a clear explanation of the deliverables, including the decided deadlines, and an explanation of who will do what. I wish she would share this presentation with us. She was inspiring to me personally in how she dealt with a difficult conversation that occurred in her session, while still maintaining a positive attitude to help us all move forward. I also wish we could have a similar update on the progress of the deliverables and the plan for the year, all included on one page, to make it clear when the ESRs will deliver a certain part of a deliverable.”

“Nice session by Marja, who participated in person for the first time. It is good to have the deliverables in mind, with deadlines and a clearer idea of what is expected of us to produce.”

“Marja's presentation was very helpful in drawing an understanding of the general vision of the framework. Also, it is valuable that the session included time for ESR's input. However, the session was a bit long and relatively unstructured - without reaching specific conclusions, but mainly brainstorming without targeting on specific questions. This led to some repetition of opinions and information.”

“Well-organised, although there is clearly an issue on how the term transdisciplinarity is understood and (over)used.”

- ESRs presentation of WP4 activity"

"It was interesting to see how each group worked on the task differently."

"It is very interesting to see how different groups understand and convey transdisciplinary co-production in the RE-DWELL project. There are still many things to be figured out but most of the contributions and interventions were insightful and I hope we will continue on this path."

"Nice variation in the presentations and useful feedback and discussion."

"Interesting points were raised through each group's discussion."

- Challenges of housing in the city of Zagreb"

"Gojko shared how privatization resulted in a lack of investment in public housing. As an architect, it was an eye opener to be aware of such a daunting challenge."

"It was a pertinent and detailed presentation that introduced us to the local context, housing struggles and the historical processes that have led to its current state."

"Great and very informative presentation. I wish there had been more time to elaborate on specific aspects, such as the role of the developers for the city of Zagreb."

"Interesting information on the local context. It would have been more interesting if the policies of the socialist era were also addressed (in a critical, comparative and even reflexive spirit)."

- "Guided tour"

"It was insightful due to the range of housing examples they showed us. This gives a better overview of the housing situation in the city. Gojko and Marko did a great job of selecting the estates and contacting residents and managers to talk about their experiences of the places."

"Three diverse visits that provided an overall very educational experience."

"Thanks to the second visit, I was shocked to realise how ""protected"" our academic environment is from extreme positions that dehumanise certain social groups and how our reflexes are hibernated when we are only exchanging with like-minded people. This has been one of the most educating experiences in Re-Dwell so far, both at a professional and at a personal level."

- Beyond the market: transforming the housing agenda in Europe

"Very interesting presentation, totally aligned with the research topic of re-dwell. Insights of an expert."

"One of the best sessions I have ever attend in RE-DWELL activities. She is so humble, enthusiastic and very knowledgeable."

"One of the highlights of the workshop. It is very interesting to hear from researchers who are not directly involved in RE-DWELL contributing to our events and activities. The concept of communities of practise is in line with the aim of RE-DWELL, to create a framework for sustainable and affordable transdisciplinary research in housing."

"Amazing context and presentation."

“Interesting and well-articulated.”

“Always interesting input from Montserrat.”

- Discussions with EAB members about presentations of previous day

“It was a necessary space to convey and express concerns or misunderstandings regarding the type of community of knowledge and practice we are creating in RE-DWELL.”

“Preparing a presentation with reflections on the previous day's discussion is itself extremely appreciated. Having had more time to prepare, it would be very useful to provide specific comments/suggestions per group, along with the general ones.”

“Useful in order to understand how much we don't understand. The problem is the problem. Additionally, the rapport between Alex and Leandro managed to make everyone uncomfortable, especially external participants that were quite unaware of the internal tensions. Marja, however, did her best to defuse the situation.”

- RMT3 introduction

“I am so grateful for both Adrienne and Lorraine as they considered all the suggestions we made in the preparation stage of this course. I appreciate that they respected about needs and it felt that they care about us and our progress.”

“It is good to see that previous feedback and suggestions made by ESRs were taken into account in the design of this module. Also, both TS3 and RMT3 are aligned and have common goals and objectives. This shows that the activities are interlinked and do not develop in silos.”

“This was a good session with information on the upcoming RMT3 course.”

“Challenging to understand - read the diagram.”

- TS3 hands on session

“Helpful exercise.”

“It brought up interesting discussions among the group members. For me I discovered new stakeholders that my research would be useful for them to be aware of.”

“It was a necessary activity to link what we had previously discussed in our groups with the rest of the ESRs. Hopefully, this can result in a compilation of stakeholders from all organisations and institutions across Europe. This could be a valuable resource for all of us in the future. And proof that new channels of communication and communities of practise have emerged with the implementation of the project.”

“The session was useful. However, we had already prepared material for the Stage 1 of the task which was not presented at all. It is a bit of a pity that we have to re-write and re-organise information. Maybe a good practice for the future (especially when we are requested to work in Miro) would be to be given the board/template in advance and been asked to work on this.”

“Good, but the Miro board was a difficult to read.”

- Portuguese residential strategies before the Carnation Revolution: designing affordable neighbourhoods

“Interesting topic, aligned with RE-DWELL.”

“I really enjoyed it. It was full of stories and lessons, and also reflected the importance of being humble with the example of architects designing houses that people did not live in, even though for architects, they were so well-designed and good. The example she shared that for some families they might feel more comfortable in places that for architects may not look that much appealing.”

“Once again, it is very interesting to exchange ideas with other researchers on housing issues at the events organised by RE-DWELL. The presentation was insightful, but a little detached from the rest of the workshop.”

“The presentation was great and Ana was a very nice surprise of this workshop. However, due to it being very context-specific and not very relevant to the workshop it is difficult to understand how the topic fits in the program.”

“Interesting, but I dislike the idea of shaping the way we live based on class. Could have benefitted from a further discussion about this concept.”

- ESRs hands-on exercise – reflective writing on previous WP4 task

“Fruitful discussion.”

“It was a helpful start to get started on the writing task. It resulted in an interesting discussion among my group, exploring how different our research approaches are. It turned out to be like a communication training, helping us to simplify how we explain our projects to each other so that we can better understand and explore links.”

“My colleagues were not able to attend the session.”

“It was nice that we took some time to discuss how to take our collaborative work one step further. Realistically for most of the groups it worked as a brainstorming, rather than writing session.”

“This task should be one A4 extended abstract (similar to the Grenoble abstracts). This would be a real exercise in collaboration and ensure all content is sharp, relevant, and academic. 5-10 pages is too much, and the prescribed red lettered instructions is arbitrary - these parts becoming a tick-box exercise, rather than actual academic content and evaluation.”

- Meetings ESRs and supervisors

“I did not have a meeting with my supervisory team because we meet often and the next meeting was the week after the workshop. However, I think it is important to have these spaces for my colleagues who do not have the same amount of supervision.”

“Nice that we have this option integrated in the program.”

“I enjoyed this, but I think it should have been an open session where ESRs can talk to any of the other supervisors - not necessarily on their project - to benefit from the network.”

“I believe that for most of us this was translated into free time, which was much appreciated after two full days of events.”

- Any other comments or suggestions for upcoming network activities (workshops, summer schools)

“Very nice activity! Helped us clarify issues and evolve our research.”

“This workshop exemplified the good progress towards keeping the schedule as planned, and we had some time to rest between the lectures/activities and the dinner.”

“I appreciated that the programme was not from nine to seven every day, but only on Wednesday due to the guided tour. This gives you the opportunity to do some work between the end of the programme and dinner. I would personally enjoy it if we could also suggest speakers for Reading.”

“I would like to thank everyone who was involved in organising this event. It was very well planned and organised. See you soon in Reading!”

“Congratulations to the organisers for such a contextually-rich workshop. Moving towards the strategizing of the transdisciplinary assessment framework, it would help that the discussions on the tasks become more structured with pragmatical goals and outputs.”

“It is a pity that people were excluded because there was no online option this time. The possibility of a blended workshop/summer school etc, should always be available.”

3. Conclusion

The Zagreb workshop enabled participants to explore the connections between various disciplines and actors resulting from the research activities carried out in the project in different contexts, including individual research projects, secondments, and collaborative research activities (vocabulary, case studies). Invited lecturers gave presentations and took a part in discussions regarding the necessity of taking a transdisciplinary approach to address sustainable and affordable housing from the policy and financing perspective. A joined activity of the courses "Research, Methods, and Tools" and "Transferable Skills" focused on strategies and tools facilitated communication and knowledge transfer between academic and non-academic actors. Site visits and lectures by local academics provided insights into policy and challenging strategies for providing affordable housing in the city of Zagreb.

The workshop was important step in strengthening consortium cohesion, acquiring new skills and knowledge with engaged discussion of all participants with commitment to contribute in achieving the project aims. Furthermore, ESRs gained a unique and valuable experience in framing a transdisciplinary perspective in their individual research and had the opportunity to discuss their doubts and perspectives with the present supervisors and other ESRs. The work carried out in this workshop will continue with the remaining activities of TS3 and RMT3 courses. It will also inform the future development of the RE-DWELL assessment framework for affordable and sustainable housing which is under development in Work Package 4.

Annex 1 –WP4 presentations

WP4 presentation from Team 1: Tijn Croon, Carolina Martin and Androniki Pappa

WP4 presentation from Team 2: Saskia Furman, Phryne Roussou and Christophe Verrier

Why a univocous understanding of transdisciplinarity doesn't work?

- This approach has limited reach in **ACADEMIA** and **PRACTICE**:
 - Sectoral knowledge is key for departments
 - Technical solutions are key for policymakers
 - Methodological developments require specialised training

Should we go back to empirics?

- Transdisciplinarity as empirics vs transdisciplinarity as normative
- Contingent on question vs necessary
- Cognizant of limitations vs idealistic

WP4 presentation from Team 5: Annette Davis, Alex Fernández and Andreas Panagidis